

Make Product Design and Development Beyond Active Learning with 'LOVE'

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Abstract

Product Design and Development has become a standard course in engineering and business master programs. The objective of this course is to provide students knowledge on a systematic product design and development process. With the new market trend and dynamic change of customer needs, the course content has been enhanced and put more emphasis on strategic design, creativity, and innovation. These changes have made an impact on the way this course should be taught. Intensive lectures with and without assignments cannot make the learning effective. Project-based learning, game-based learning, and university-industry teaching collaboration are some examples of active learning methods that have been promoted for delivering this course. They aim to provide practical and hands-on learning experiences for students. However, the students may or may not gain the learning experience as expected. Reasons are, for example, improper designed learning activities, improper preparation and execution process, the mismatch between teaching and learning styles, and undesirable learning environments. Therefore, this paper presents a framework of designing learning activities in the view of the student learning experience journey considering three key components of the learning experience: functional component, mechanic component, and humanic component. In order to ensure that the journey is dedicated to the cultivation of a strong learning experience, a recently developed learning experience model, 'LOVE', is incorporated. The proposed framework was implemented through the intensive product design and development course offerings at Tunghai University, Taiwan. Fifteen students attended the course. They were asked to provide feedback at the end of each session to keep track of their learning progress and crosscheck the effectiveness of the proposed process. According to their feedback, various dimensions of the courses were rated on the range of 'most satisfied' and many positive comments were also reported.

Keywords: Effective learning; Learning experience; Student Learning Experience Journey; Learning Experience Component; Product Design and Development; LOVE.

1 Introduction

Product design and development (PDD) has been playing important roles to drive and sustain the growth of businesses. How a product should be designed to be competitive and effectively respond to the customer needs as well as being survived in the fierce market is not easy. It requires a strategic thinking and systematic approach. The impact of well-designed products can also be seen as a mechanism that drives industries and the economy. Therefore, a course on PDD has been taught globally in different schools, from engineering to business at undergraduate and graduate levels. The content of the courses offered in different universities is adjusted according to the education level and the area of specializations.

As the customer needs are always dynamic and the advancement of technology expedites the capability to develop a new product, the course content has always been updated. Academic and practical researches in various dimensions - under the product design and development umbrella - rapidly produce up-to-date topics that can be integrated into the course. Besides the well-accepted literature developed by Ulrich (2003), many new topics, for example, Blue Ocean Strategy, Kano Questionnaire, and Quality Function Deployment (QFD) have been added to the PDD course offered at Department of Industrial Systems Engineering, Asian Institute of Technology, Thailand. The up-to-date course content, however, shall not be considered as the only key element that provides an effective learning experience for students to achieve the course learning outcomes and expected competencies. Teaching and learning methods is another crucial factor. How the course should be taught must also be considered. The regular lecture is perceived to be inadequate for deeper understanding, complex problem-solving skills, and creativity (Sajjad, 2010). According to that, the active learning approach

has been promoted (Shekar, 2007). For example, at Gazi University (Turkey), students learned the industrial design course through the project-based learning method. The students were put in teams to collaboratively design an equipment bag for cycling, hiking, and mountain climbing sports with users (Yalman & Yavuzcan, 2015). At the University of Twente (Netherlands), the teaching format used to deliver the course product design was adjusted. In addition to the regular lectures, game-based learning, and practical workshops were also employed to provide practical and hands-on learning experience to students (Becker & Wits, 2014).

However, there are two sides to every coin. The active learning approach also has both pros and cons. Requesting students to play an active role in an activity may produce negative learning experience and lessens the enthusiasm in their learning if, for example, the activity disconnects them to the real-world practice. A student survey on a product design course reveals that students preferred fewer exercises with more depth. They mentioned that they would like to apply tools more on the design of a real product instead of analyzing existing products (Becker & Wits, 2014). This issue can be alleviated by applying the LOVE model (Hussadintorn Na Ayutthaya & Koomsap, 2017) which proposes designing balanced learning activities based not only on the level of student involvement but also on how the activity connects students to the learning process to cultivate a strong learning experience. In addition to that, an execution plan is also important to properly deliver the designed learning activities and avoid undesirable learning environment.

Therefore, this paper proposes a framework, in which the LOVE model is integrated, to design learning activities in the view of the student learning experience journey. The framework also considers three key components of the learning experience: functional component, mechanic component, and humanic component.

The framework was implemented through the intensive product design and development course offered at Tunghai University, Taiwan. To keep track of student learning progress and crosscheck the effectiveness of the proposed framework, fifteen students who attended the course were asked to provide feedback at the end of each session. According to their feedback, various dimensions of the courses were rated on the range of 'most satisfied' and many positive comments were also reported.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows. In section 2, the LOVE model and its application are presented. The proposed framework is explained in section 3. Section 4 illustrates the implementation of the proposed framework to the intensive product design and development course and the student feedback. Conclusions are provided in section 5.

2 LOVE Model

The LOVE Model (Figure 1) describes that learning experiences along a learning journey are stimulated based on how students involve into a learning activity – depending upon the type of approach used by teachers, methods and tools used, and also on students' attitude – and how the activity connects students to the learning process. These two dimensions termed as student involvement (passive/active involvement) and nature of learning (absorption/immersion). In term of the nature of learning, absorption occurs when a teacher brings knowledge to the students while immersion occurs when students bring themselves to get involved to obtain the knowledge. Learning experience, therefore, is categorized into four realms: L-learner, O-observer, V-visitor, and E-experimenter.

Figure 1. LOVE Model (Hussadintorn Na Ayutthaya and Koomsap, 2017).

Learner role implies active engagement of students but with rather specific, teacher originating, content. Observer role is a passive type of experience that is also made on teacher-based content. Visitor role is also passive but the circumstances are not ordinary ones and students can get immersed with the experience that is not, or not completely, prepared by the teacher. Experimenter role is both active and immerse type of experience that gives students partially or fully opportunity to use its own understanding and competences to participate and create the experience. In order to attain to researcher role, students must gain a variety of experiences which are transformative, influential, practical, effective and memorable to shape their research capability (Hussadintorn Na Ayutthaya & Koomsap, 2018). The outcome of this transformation is changing students from knowledge consumers to knowledge producers (Lovitts, 2005; Gardener, 2008). LOVE model suggests to include all type of experiences in studying programs and in specific courses. Balancing the experiences, which nowadays means including more active and more immersive approaches in education, should give the best results (Prince, 2004; Freeman et al., 2014).

Since some of teaching and learning methods, by their characteristics, share some similarities resulted in providing the same type of learning experience. The teaching and learning methods, collected from literatures, have been classified into four different categories of experiences (Hussadintorn Na Ayutthaya et al., 2019), as illustrated in Figure 2, to assist instructors for the selection of teaching and learning methods.

 E-Experimenting (active immersion)	
1. Field classes, trips and excursions 2. Conference 3. Virtual reality	1. Project-based learning (PjBL) 2. Laboratory classes 3. Virtual laboratory
 L-Learning (active absorption)	
1. Lecture 2. Guided conversation 3. Integrated or interdisciplinary teaching 4. Showing video material 5. Seminars conducted in classes 6. Live lecture from a remote place	1. Discussion 2. Demonstration with exercising 3. Class debate 4. Small groups debate 5. Simulation 6. Problem-based learning (PrBL) 7. Programmed teaching 8. Workshop 9. Brainstorming 10. Case study 11. Online interactive learning 12. Game-based learning 13. Guided practical exercises 14. Role play 15. Assignments 16. Individual presentation

Figure 2. Teaching and Learning Methods on LOVE grid (Hussadintorn Na Ayutthaya et al., 2019).

3 Proposed Framework

An effective learning experience journey that students walkthrough to complete a course to achieve the expected knowledge, skills, and competence is the result of their interactions with the three key components of the learning experience (Figure 3). They are (1.) functional component: proper course content, (2.) humanic component: the ability of instructors to transfer knowledge and implement their teaching ability within a variety of learning activities, (3.) mechanic component: the variety of teaching and learning methods that stimulate the LOVE experience, and desirable learning environments.

If any component is omitted, the learning journey will be undesirable and ineffective. For example, when the course content is up-to-date, but the course is delivered in the traditional lecture-based teaching method. The course, therefore, does not provide any hands-on and practical experience that supports student competence development. In another case, when functional component and mechanic component are properly design, but the instructors cannot implement the designed modern activities. This causes a poor learning journey. The students gain improper learning experiences and have difficulty in completing the course.

Therefore, this paper proposes a design framework that begins with designing proper course content. The content should be up-to-date. The topics are aligned with the course learning outcomes and connect students to theory, tools, applications, and practices. Next is selecting proper teaching and learning methods. The proper result of this step is a set of learning activities that stimulates LOVE learning experience to students. The last step dedicates to the execution plan. The learning environment should support the implementation of designed learning activities. The result of this framework produces an effective learning experience journey for students. The designed journey does not only benefit the instructor to prepare and deliver the course but also assist students to properly prepare themselves to attend the class. The level of student involvement also signals students to be enthusiastic and get involved in the activities.

Figure 3. Key components affecting the learning experience.

4 Illustration on Intensive Product Design and Development Course

This section illustrates the implementation of the proposed framework on the intensive product design and development course.

4.1 Product Design and Development Course (PDD)

This is a 1-credit intensive course completed within four days. The course was offered at Tunghai University, Taiwan. The objective of this course is to provide students knowledge on a systematic approach for product design and development process. Students, on the completion of this course, were expected to: (1.) analyze products offered in a market for their effectiveness and (2.) develop a mission statement according to the identified business opportunity. The topics covered in this course are presented in Figure 4. In this course, the

students will learn and practice how to systematically design products in a team environment. It is a participant-centered learning course that the students actively involve.

4.2 Designed Learning Experience Journey

As the course content has already been updated, the design process for this intensive course focused on selecting appropriate teaching and learning methods and designing a proper learning environment. The process started with understanding the student profile and background. The majority of students who registered for this course were undergraduate students. A few of them were Ph.D. students. Their areas of specialization were different. This course was new to them. Therefore, the instructor selected a simple product that all students could easily work on for their group project work. It was a vending machine (VM).

The duration of each class was within three hours excepting the class on the 4th day which was separated into two sessions – morning and afternoon. The number of course topics that were taught each day was distributed based on scope, depth, and class duration. Teaching methods used for each class were selected to provide a variety of learning experiences and balance the level of student involvement in the learning activities.

Figure 4 presents the designed learning journey for this intensive course. On the 1st day, the class began with group work on designing a VM. The students assigned into three groups. Without any lecture, each group applied their knowledge to design a VM. Then, the gallery walk was conducted. The class visited each group to listen to its short presentation. The groups received feedback from the instructor and classmates. After that, the groups were asked to discuss among the members and compare their ideas with other groups. The class ended with the lecture on the Introduction to PDD. The students started realizing how a product should be designed and perceived the importance of PDD.

*VM: Vending Machine, PDD: Product Design and Development

Figure 4. Designed Learning Journey for the Intensive Product Design and Development Course.

On the 2nd day, the class began with a lecture followed by a case study in which the students worked in groups to apply their knowledge gained from the lecture to the case study. Their ideas were presented to other groups through the gallery walk activity. The discussion among the members was the place for them to compare and reflect the pros and cons of their designed strategy canvases. The instructor continued the class with the lecture on the mission statement and asked the students to practice in the groups by identifying the mission statement for their VM. The instructor visited all the groups to provide supervision.

On the 3rd day, the class began with the lecture on translating the voice of the customer to customer need followed by the implementation in their group projects on designing the VM. Supervision from the instructor was provided during the group work. The class ended with the lectures on the Kano questionnaire and QFD. For the last day, the morning session began with the lecture on the last topic of the course. Then, the class played three games related to the PDD. The games aimed to push the students to think outside the box and stimulate their creativity. After lunch, the students were asked to continue on their group project and prepare for the class presentation. After a few hours, each group presented their project to the class. The other groups made comments and the instructor provided feedback to all the group at the end. The last activity was showing examples of products developed for blind people. It aimed to provide the overall picture of the PDD process to the students.

It can be seen that the learning journey provides the four types of the learning experience (LOVE). At the beginning, the students played the roles of learners and observers. When they started working on their group projects, they were immersed in the real applications of the theory. Their roles were changed to be experimenters. When attending the class presentation, their roles lied into two dimensions. Delivering the presentation put them in the experimenter role. Their roles changed to visitors when listening to the other groups' presentations.

For the level of student involvement – based on the type of learning experience stimulated by different activities, it was varied and fluctuated. The students were demanded low involvement in lecture and gallery walk; medium involvement in the first trial of designing a VM and in the game-based learning activity; high involvement in case study, project work, and class presentation.

In terms of classroom layout and facility, the classroom was arranged in a U-shape layout composing of fifteen seats – five seats on each side. The size of the room was medium to facilitate the discussion and communication during the classes without using microphones. Equipment for lectures was provided. The lighting system and the sound system supported showing video materials. The Wi-Fi connection was available to all. The stationery such as post-it notes, paper sheets, and markers was always available for the students. The designed journey does not only benefit the instructor to prepare and deliver the course but also assist the students to properly prepare themselves before attending the class. The level of student involvement also signals students to be enthusiastic and get involved in the activities.

4.3 Implementation and Student Feedback

The designed journey has been implemented. Fifteen students attended the course. Figure 5 displays the class ambiance from various activities conducted during the classes. The classroom was arranged in a U-shape layout according to the design. All the designed learning activities were conducted. However, the students sometimes were already exhausted from their other classes. In order to have student enthusiastic in collaborating with the designed learning activities, especially for some of the activities that demand high level of involvement, the instructor normally provided refreshment and applied 5-minute or 10-minute breaks. Therefore, the average level of student involvement along the whole journey closed to the expectation.

At the end of each day, the students were asked to complete the online survey developed in each particular class. To keep track of the students' learning progress, they were asked to report what they have gained from each class and their pain points during the class activities. The course teaching assistant collected the data and reported it to the instructor every day. On the first day, some students reported having difficulty in listening because they were not familiar with the instructor's accent and his speaking speed. According to that, the

instructor spoke slower. When students reported that they were not clear on some topics, the instructor revisited those topics in the following classes. Table 1 presents the students' reports on what they have obtained from the last session of the course. It can be considered as a reflection which shows that the students could achieve the course learning outcomes.

To monitor the quality of every class, the students were also asked to provide feedbacks on various dimensions covering three aspects: functional component (1. Quality of content), mechanic component (2. Quality of teaching methods, 3. Quality of teaching materials, 4. Quality of classroom infrastructure and facility, 5. Quality of learning environment during the class), and humanic component (6. Performance of the instructor, 7. Style of the instructor). Table 2 shows that, overall, the student satisfaction on this course is very high (1: least satisfied, 5: most satisfied). The overall score of all dimensions increased day by day. The students also rated very high score on recommending this course to their friends.

Figure 5. Class ambiance.

Table 1. What Students Obtained from the Last Session.

No.	Please explain what have you obtained from this session? (at the end of the 4th day)
1	How to make a mission statement, target the market, and design is not as simple as that. If we have a clear design, the next step will be not hard.
2	We finally summarized our mission statement and present our vending machine product design based on the mission statement.
3	The main idea of design is considering the fact of your product.
4	The big picture of how to design and develop the product.
5	Teamwork on product design.
6	Good at thinking.
7	Really helpful!
8	Know what customer need is the most important thing about product design.
9	What is the difference between my vision and others'.
10	To know what customers want, to design what they really need.
11	I have learned about how important teamwork is, and how difficult a team to make decision and make it happen.
12	I understand that when working on product design, I must put aside my prejudices and think about multi-faceted or cross-disciplinary possibilities.
13	How to design a good product for customer.

Table 2. Student Satisfaction on the Intensive Product Design and Development Course.

Dimension	1 st day	2 nd day	3 rd day	4 th day
	n=15	n=12	n=13	n=13
1. Quality of content	4.53	4.75	4.85	4.85
2. Quality of teaching methods	4.60	4.83	4.77	4.77
3. Quality of teaching materials	4.33	4.83	4.69	4.69
4. Quality of classroom infrastructure and facility	4.33	4.50	4.69	4.77
5. Quality of learning environment during the class	4.40	4.75	4.69	4.62
6. Performance of the instructor	4.67	4.67	4.85	4.77
7. Style of the instructor	4.47	4.75	4.85	4.85
8. How likely are you to recommend this course to your friends or colleagues?				

5 Conclusions

The student learning journey-based design framework has been developed. In order to ensure that students do achieve the course learning outcomes, their learning experience journey must be properly designed. The journey shall be designed to provide the four learning experience types (LOVE) and balance the level of student involvement in the designed activities. Many key components that contribute to stimulating learning experience have to be considered, from course content, teaching and learning methods, learning environments to the role and style of the instructor. The designed journey does not only benefit the instructor to better prepare and deliver the course but also provide a guideline for students to properly prepare themselves before attending the class. The level of student involvement also stimulates student self-regulation and raises their awareness in collaboration along the learning journey.

The proposed framework, according to the implementation and results of the student survey, presents its effectiveness and potential to be applied in other courses.

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7 References

- Becker, J. J., & Wits, W. (2014). An Experience-Based Approach to Teaching Product Design. In DS 78: Proceedings of the 16th International conference on Engineering and Product Design Education (E&PDE14), Design Education and Human Technology Relations, University of Twente, The Netherlands, 04-05.09. 2014 (pp. 688-693).
- Freeman, S., Eddy, S. L., McDonough, M., Smith, M. K., Okoroafor, N., Jordt, H., & Wenderoth, M. P. (2014). Active learning increases student performance in science, engineering, and mathematics. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 111(23), 8410-8415. doi:10.1073/pnas.1319030111
- Gardner, S. K. (2008). "What's too much and what's too little?": the process of becoming an independent researcher in doctoral education, *The Journal of Higher Education*, vol. 79(3), 2008, pp. 326-350.

- Hussadintorn Na Ayutthaya, D., & Koomsap, P. (2017). Assessment of student learning experience with 'LOVE', In: 11th International Technology, Education and Development Conference, Valencia, pp.1973-1982.
- Hussadintorn Na Ayutthaya, D., & Koomsap, P. (2018). An Application of 'LOVE' Model for Assessing Research Experience, In M. Peruzzini (Ed.), *Trandisciplinary Engineering Methods for Social Innovation of Industry 4.0* (pp. 712-720). doi: 10.3233/978-1-61499-898-3-712
- Hussadintorn Na Ayutthaya, D., Koomsap, P., Lima, R. M., & Nitkiewicz, T. (2019). Learning Experience from Teaching and Learning Methods in Engineering Education: Instructors' Viewpoint, In: 13th International Technology, Education and Development Conference, Valencia.
- Lovitts*, B. E. (2005). Being a good course-taker is not enough: a theoretical perspective on the transition to independent research, *Studies in higher education*, vol. 30(2), 2005, pp. 137–154.
- Prince, M. (2004). Does Active Learning Work? A review of the Research. *Journal of Engineering Education*, 93(3), 223-231.
- Sajjad, S. (2010). Effective teaching methods at higher education level, *Pakistan Journal of Special Education*, vol. 11, pp. 29–43.
- Shekar, A. (2007). Active learning and reflection in product development engineering education. *European Journal of Engineering Education*, 32(2), 125-133. doi: 10.1080/03043790601118705
- Ulrich, K. T. (2003). *Product design and development*. Tata McGraw-Hill Education.
- Yalman, Z., & Yavuzcan, H. G. (2015). Co-Design Practice in Industrial Design Education in Turkey A Participatory Design Project. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 197, 2244-2250.